

STRUCTURAL RELIABILITY OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Statistical calculations have been made for the static load reliability of an aircraft fleet assuming typical metallic and composite strength distributions. A factor of safety is defined as the element strength divided by the "weakest of the fleet" strength. Element strength is typical "A" or "B" basis material allowables. "Weakest of the fleet" strength is calculated statistically assuming each aircraft to be made up of a realistic arrangement (in-series or in-parallel) of critical elements. Similar preliminary calculations are also made for fatigue life. It is shown that the reliability of the current damage tolerant design, such as multiple load path and crack stoppers, can be specified in quantitative terms. The scatter of the strength of an aircraft structure is smaller than that of its elements. Freudenthal's results on scatter factor are overly conservative.

INTRODUCTION

A statistical approach to the design criteria for aircraft structure of composite material is proposed. It is based on the concept of a specified probability (or reliability) that the strength of the weakest one of a "fleet" of n structures will exceed a certain value. It may be called the weakest-in-the-fleet approach. It shares certain similarities with the "time-to-first-failure" approach introduced by Freudenthal, with two major differences. First, the present approach is applicable to both static strength and fatigue life, whereas Freudenthal only covered the fatigue case. Secondly, the present approach recognizes the existence of redundancy and multiple load path in the structure (in-parallel arrangement) and thus the scatter of values of strength and life among replica structures is less than that in the components or elements of the structure. We shall show that because of this, Freudenthal's results are overly conservative and give an unnecessarily large value for scatter factor, or factor of safety.

The current U.S. Air Force and Navy structural design criteria is based on the assumption that metal aircraft structure has small flaws, defects, and cracks at delivery, (See Refs. 1 to 5). To ensure that the structure will last the required service life, two damage tolerant design approaches are allowed, the fail-safe approach, and the slow-crack growth approach. In the fail-safe approach, unstable crack is locally contained by multiple load paths, or tear stoppers. In the slow-crack growth approach, the cracks are prevented from attaining the critical size for unstable rapid propagation.

These criteria are not suitable for structures of composite materials because the failure modes of composites are more complicated than simple cracks and flaws. Also, the scatter of static strength and fatigue life for composites is much larger than that for metals. Figure 1 shows the ranges of scatter for metals and composites in terms of coefficient of variation and Weibull shape parameter. For composites, a statistical approach, which can specify in quantitative terms the probability of survival, is needed. Freudenthal's "time-to-first-failure" concept is one of the statistical reliability approaches.

Freudenthal assumes that among a fleet of identical aircraft, the first catastrophic failure is of most concern. Therefore, the expected time to the failure of the first aircraft is used, instead of the current practice of using mean time to failure and a scatter factor. The reliability of the fleet is dependent on the fleet size. If each aircraft in the fleet has a fixed and identical reliability, then the larger the fleet size, the smaller the expected time to first failure, which can be calculated by the weakest-link theory, or extreme-value distribution theory.

In our present approach, we shall study the effect of multiple-load path, tear-stopper, and redundant structure, on the reliability of the fleet. The fleet will be considered as consisting of n aircraft (or n structures). Each aircraft will be assumed to have m components. Each component has a two-parameter Weibull strength distribution. The components will be assumed as arranged either in-series, or in-parallel. In the series case, if one component fails the whole aircraft is considered failed. In the parallel case, if one component fails, the rest of the components would share the load equally. The parallel arrangement is essentially the multiple-load path, tear-stopper, or redundancy approaches in "damage tolerance." In actual cases, the components are in a combination of series-parallel arrangements. We shall also assume the load is of a fixed value (deterministic) and the components are independent.

CURRENT STATUS OF STRUCTURAL RELIABILITY

The current criteria are basically deterministic, and are originally for metal structures. For static loads, the limit load is defined as the maximum operational load expected to be encountered. The ultimate load is equal to the limit load times a factor of safety, which is generally not less than 1.5. Two allowable stresses are used (MIL-HDBK-5) [6], for primary structures the "A" allowable is used, (at least 99% of the population must have values above the A-allowable with 95% confidence). For secondary structure, the B-allowable is used, (at least 90% of the population must have values above the B-allowable with 95% confidence). The material yield allowable stresses shall not be exceeded at the limit load level; the

material must sustain ultimate load without failure. The fatigue load spectrum should be based on the planned operational usage of the vehicle. The fatigue life of the structure must exceed one service life-time multiplied by a scatter factor. The scatter factor used by the USAF is 4, or larger, under average load spectrum. The U.S. Navy uses a scatter factor of 2 under extreme load spectrum.

The current criteria recognize that aircraft structure has small flaws, defects, and cracks at delivery. To ensure that the structure will last the required service life, two damage tolerant design approaches are available, the fail-safe approach, and the slow-crack growth approach. In the fail-safe approach, unstable crack growth is locally contained by multiple load paths, or crack stoppers. In the slow-crack growth approach, the cracks are prevented from attaining the critical size for unstable rapid propagation during the life of the structure, or between inspection intervals.

Among the few proposed structural criteria, we shall mention the concept of "time-to-first failure" proposed by Freudenthal [7] [8], and the concept of treating the reliability at three levels: the components, the structure, and the fleet, as proposed by Rogers, et al. [9] (the so-called NASA Monograph Rationale).

Freudenthal's concept is that among a fleet of identical aircraft, the first catastrophic failure of one aircraft is of most concern. Therefore, the expected time to first failure is used instead of the current practice mean time to failure. The reliability of the fleet is dependent on the fleet size. If each aircraft in the fleet has a fixed and identical reliability, then the larger the fleet size, the smaller the expected time to first failure, which can be calculated by the weakest-link theory, or extreme-value distribution theory.

In Roger's approach, the reliability of the fleet is calculated from that of the aircraft, which in turn is calculated from the reliability of the components of the aircraft. (It also stipulates that the component can be further divided into subcomponents and elements. The method of calculation from one level to the next is always the same). The reliability of the fleet is calculated by the weakest-link theory; if one of the aircraft in a fleet fails, the fleet is considered "failed."

We shall call this an in-series model. They treated the relation between aircraft reliability and the component reliability in the same manner, that is, if one component fails, the aircraft is considered failed. This is again an in-series model. No redundant component is considered. Nor are fail-safe measures, such as multiple load path and crack stoppers, considered in the reliability calculation.

We may also mention that the concept of treating reliability by levels of aircraft, component, subcomponent and element is used by the Navy and mentioned by Weinberger, Somoroff, and Riley in [5]. Other pertinent work on aircraft reliability may be found in Refs. [10]-[13]. In [13], Lemon and Manning give a brief overview of the structural reliability problem, and a list of selected references. This list includes all relevant articles on structural reliability up to 1974.

STATIC LOAD RELIABILITY

Let us consider a fleet of n aircraft. We are interested in the weakest aircraft in the fleet. We shall calculate, with a certain reliability (say 95%), the strength of the weakest aircraft; or the load that will fail the weakest aircraft with 95% probability.

We shall study the strength of a primary structure of the aircraft, such as wing torque box, stabilizer, or fuselage. Failure of this structure is considered fatal to the aircraft. This structure consists of m components. For the wing torque box, the components could be the spars. Figure 2 shows a typical wing box structure of the advanced Harrier and its spars. For simplicity, we shall assume the m components are arranged either in-series, or in-parallel. For the in-series arrangement, if one component fails, the whole structure and thus, the aircraft fail. In the in-parallel case, if one component fails, the other components can still support the load. The parallel arrangement is essentially the multiple-load path, crack stopper, or redundancy approaches in "damage tolerance." In actual cases, the components are in a combination of series-parallel arrangements. For instance, the spars of the Harrier wing torque box can sustain the limit load after one auxiliary spar fails. We shall also assume the load is of a fixed value (deterministic) and the components are independent. A summary of the series-parallel arrangement is given in Table I.

Table I. Statistical Series and Parallel Arrangements of Elements				
Features Arrangements	Graphical representation	Principle	Examples	Theory and equations
n-elements in-series		the whole unit is considered failed when one of its elements fails.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • elements physically in-series • brittle material • aircraft in a fleet 	weakest link theory; simple equation.
n-elements in-parallel		surviving elements can still sustain the load.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • elements physically in-parallel • multiple-load path • redundant structure • tear stopper • softening strip • test coupon to large structures 	static-bundle theory fatigue - theory to be developed.

The strength of the component is assumed to be of two-parameter Weibull distribution, or

$$F_{\Sigma}(\sigma) = P(\Sigma \leq \sigma) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{\beta}}\right)^{\alpha}\right] \quad (1)$$

where

Σ = component strength random variable

σ = value of Σ

F = cumulative distribution function

P = probability

σ_{β} = scale parameter (characteristic strength of component)

α = shape parameter

If the m components are in-series, the distribution of strength of the structure is

$$F_{\Sigma_m}(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left[-m\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{\beta}}\right)^{\alpha}\right] \quad (2)$$

If the m components are in-parallel, the strength distribution of the structure cannot be expressed in simple form. For small values of m, the exact distribution can be calculated numerically. In Ref. [14], equations for the distributions for values of m up to seven are presented; they are based on the uniform sharing of load by surviving components (no stress-concentration).

In Ref. [15], the bundle strength distribution has also been expressed in a recursion formula, (Eq. 9.2). We have used this formula and calculated the in-parallel distribution for values of m up to 20. For the case of m = 50, we used the simplified large bundle equation of Daniel. Symbolically, we may express the strength distribution of a structure with m in-parallel components as

$$F_{\Sigma_m}(\sigma) = \text{function}(\alpha, \sigma_{\beta}, m) \quad (3)$$

The strength of the aircraft will be considered the same as the strength of this structure. We are interested in the weakest in a fleet of n aircraft. The distribution of strength of this weakest aircraft in terms of the parameters of the component is

$$F_{\Sigma mn} = 1 - \exp\left[-mn \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_\beta}\right)^\alpha\right] \quad (4)$$

for m in-series components, and

$$F_{\Sigma m'n} = 1 - [1 - F_{\Sigma m'}(\sigma)]^n \quad (5)$$

for m in-parallel components.

For a certain value of reliability, the strength of the weakest-of-the-fleet can be calculated. We shall consider 95% reliability in this derivation.

Let

$$\sigma_{wf} = \text{strength of the weakest aircraft in the fleet with 95\% reliability,} \quad (6)$$

then, for the in-series case,

$$F_{\Sigma mn} = 0.05 = 1 - \exp\left[-mn \left(\frac{\sigma_{wf}}{\sigma_\beta}\right)^\alpha\right] \quad (7)$$

or

$$\frac{\sigma_{wf}}{\sigma_\beta} = \left[\frac{1}{mn} \ln\left(\frac{1}{0.95}\right) \right]^{1/\alpha} \quad (8)$$

For the in-parallel case,

$$[1 - F_{\Sigma m'}(\sigma_{wf})]^n = 0.95 \quad (9)$$

In Figures 3 and 4 we have plotted the cumulative distribution of strength of the component F_{Σ} , with $\alpha = 10$. Also plotted are the strength distribution of the aircraft with seven components either in-parallel, $F_{\Sigma m'}$, or in-series, $F_{\Sigma m}$. The distributions of the weakest of 100 aircraft, $F_{\Sigma mn}$ and $F_{\Sigma m'n}$ are shown in Figure 4.

Calculations of $\sigma_{wf}/\sigma_{\beta}$ are made for $\alpha = 2, 5, 10$, and 20 and $m = 7$ for both in-series and in-parallel arrangements. These results are plotted in Figures 5 and 6, as $\sigma_{wf}/\sigma_{\beta}$ versus curves.

In order to gain more insight, let us define a Factor of Safety (F.S.) as

$$\text{Factor of Safety} = \frac{\sigma_{0.95}}{\sigma_{wf}} \quad (10)$$

where $\sigma_{0.95}$ is the strength that 95% of the component will exceed, or

$$0.95 = \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma_{0.95}}{\sigma_{\beta}}\right)^{\alpha}\right] \quad (11)$$

It may also be considered as the allowable stress of the component. In general, a designer will use this as the strength, and will not apply a stress that will exceed this. Now, due to the series arrangement of the aircraft in the fleet, the weakest of the fleet has a strength much less than the 95% reliability strength of the component, $\sigma_{0.95}$, or $\sigma_{wf} < \sigma_{0.95}$. The ratio $\sigma_{0.95}/\sigma_{wf}$, which we call F.S., is the factor of safety required, such that no failure of the fleet would occur with 95% reliability. Looking at it another way, if the applied stress is restricted to

$$\text{applied stress} \leq \sigma_{0.95}/\text{F.S.} \quad (12)$$

then

$$\text{applied stress} \leq \sigma_{wf} \quad (13)$$

This would assure that no failure of the fleet with 95% reliability.

We have used 95% reliability for illustration purposes. For other values of reliability, such as 99%, similar calculations can be made.

The factor of safety as defined above is plotted as a function of n in Figures 7 and 8. We have used $m = 7$, or seven components in the structure, which closely simulates the eight spars in the Harrier wing torque box. Figure 7, a value of $\alpha = 20$ is used, which is representative of the shape parameter of static strength of metal structures. Two curves are plotted, one for in-series arrangement, one for in-parallel. As mentioned before, the actual arrangement is a combination of these two, represented by points within the area between these two curves. It can be seen that the present practice of using a factor of safety of 1.5 is sufficient to ensure no failure for a few thousand aircraft in the fleet.

The dotted line in Figure 7 is plotted with the assumption that the shape parameter of the aircraft is the same as that of the component. It may also be considered as an aircraft with only one component. The characteristic strength, σ_B , is used in the formula, instead of the 95% reliable strength $\sigma_{0.95}$. It can be seen that a larger factor of safety would be required in this case. We labeled this curve by Freudenthal, because it follows the basic approach he used for the fatigue case.

Figure 7. Factor of Safety Required for No Failure of Any Aircraft in the Fleet with 95% Reliability. Typical Metal Structure

Figure 8 shows similar curves for a shape parameter of 10, typical for strength of composite materials. Here, a factor of safety of 1.5 is adequate for a few thousand aircraft in the fleet if the components are essentially in-parallel. Thus, it is seen that it is more important to have multiple load path, or crack stopper in composite material structures than in metal structures.

Curves for other values of m , as well as further discussion on the advantage of in-parallel arrangement may be found in Ref. [16].

FATIGUE RELIABILITY

For the in-series arrangement, the formulas for the fatigue case are the same as those for the static case. For the parallel arrangement, the fatigue situation is more complicated than the static case. We shall present here results of a preliminary investigation.

We assume that the $S-N_B$ curve of the component is known, where S is the maximum stress of the fatigue load and N_B is the characteristic value of the fatigue life. Also, the life distribution at a given stress level is assumed to be a two-parameter Weibull, or

$$F(N) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{N}{N_B}\right)^\alpha\right]. \tag{14}$$

For simplicity, we shall also assume that the shape parameter is the same at all stress levels, and only the scale parameter, or characteristic life N_B , changes with the stress level.

Figure 9 shows a typical $S-N_B$ curve. Let us consider a structure with seven components in parallel. Under the initial stress S , the characteristic life of the components is N_B . After one component fails, the stress level is increased to $7S/6$, and the corresponding characteristic life is N_B^1 . After three component failures, the stress in the remaining is $7S/4$, and the characteristic life N_B^3 .

With this information, and the recursion formula given by Daniel, we have calculated the life distribution of the aircraft with m component either in-series, or in-parallel. The life of the weakest in a fleet of n aircraft is also calculated.

We shall define the Scatter Factor (S.F.) as

$$S.F. = \frac{N_{0.95}}{N_{wf}} \quad (15)$$

where

$N_{0.95}$ = 95% reliable life of the component

N_{wf} = 95% reliable life of the weakest in a fleet of n aircraft

Note that Freudenthal used the characteristic life N_B , instead of $N_{0.95}$, as his definition of scatter factor, and he did not consider the aircraft as consisting of m components. He used a shape parameter of 4 for the aircraft fatigue life, which is overly conservative. The shape parameter for metal specimens is around 4; the shape parameter of the aircraft with more than one component in parallel must have a shape parameter of more than 4.

In Figure 10, we have plotted the scatter factor for seven components with a shape parameter of 4. In this case, the series and parallel arrangement curves are not distinguishable. For a fleet of 100 aircraft, from our analysis an S.F. of 5 would be adequate, whereas Freudenthal's approach requires a value of 7.

Figure 10. Scatter Factor Required for No Fatigue Failure of any Aircraft in the Fleet, with 95% Reliability, Typical Metal Structure with Seven Components.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. In comparison with metals, composite materials have more scatter in static strength and fatigue life. Thus, more extensive statistical study is needed for reliability of composite structures, than for metals.
2. The current damage tolerance design in using multiple load paths and crack stoppers is statistically in-parallel arrangement of components. The reliability of aircraft structures with this type of design can be calculated quantitatively, and should be done in the future.
3. Freudenthal was overly pessimistic. He did not realize the benefit of the in-parallel arrangement. The shape parameter of the structure can be larger than that of the component. Unnecessarily high values of scatter factor are not needed.
4. A large panel can be considered as made up of many small "coupons." These coupons are in a combination of series-parallel arrangements. The shape parameter of the panel most likely is larger than that of the coupon. This effect should be studied.

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